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Research Article

Formulation And Evaluation on Oil Removing Herbal Soap

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ABSTRACT

Health benefits of honey have been reported in a variety of conditions including microbial infections, wound healing, inflammation, glucose tolerance and analgesia. Honey is a supersaturated sugar solution mainly comprised of D- fructose, D-glucose, sucrose, maltose and higher sugars (80% of solid mass). While other natural products i.e. alkaloids, flavonoids/isoflavones, glycosides, phenolics, peptides/proteins are present in minor quantities. A number of enzymes such as invertase, amylase and glucose oxidase have been found in honey. Antibacterial and antifungal activities of honey are well documented and characterized. These antimicrobial properties have been related to oligosaccharides, glycopeptides and peptides present in honey. Honey glucose oxidase provides a continuous and slow release of hydrogen peroxide at a level which is antibacterial but not tissue-damaging. Daily skin care routines for patients in acute and long-term care facilities include washing, bathing, and showering, which is frequently followed by the use of lotions, creams, and/or ointments. Although these skin care and personal hygiene routines are essential to nursing practice, little is known about their advantages or clinical effectiveness. This article's objectives were to design a clinical algorithm for basic skin care and to review the empirical evidence supporting the procedures and interventions for basic skin care. Herbal soap preparation is a medicine or drug like medicinal properties which is antibacterial, antifungal bring the skin and may property. The crude drug which used in the soap preparation is given many property medicine.

INTRODUCTION

Cosmetics are constituted mixtures of chemical compounds derived from either natural sources, or synthetically created ones. Cosmetics have various

purposes. Those designed for personal care and skin care can be used to cleanse or protect the body or skin. Cosmetics designed to enhance or alter one's appearance can be used to conceal blemishes,

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enhance one's natural features (such as the eyebrows and eyelashes), add colour to a person's face, or change the appearance of the face entirely to resemble a different person, creature or object. Cosmetics can also be designed to add fragrance to the body. Herbal soap preparation is a medicine or drug like medicinal properties which is antibacterial, antifungal bring the skin and may property. The crude drug which used in the soap preparation is given many property medicine.

Soap

Soap is simply that salt of fatty acids. When it comes to soap, the acid that is used generally comes in the form of fatty animal acids derived from and plants. So now we know, that soap is a salt that is created when a fatty acid is combined with an alkali. We know what fatty acids and alkalis are. When soap is combined with water, it acts as a surfactant. A surfactant molecule has oil soluble and water-soluble parts. Because of this, these molecules can surround grease or dirt

particles and bring them into the water so they can be washed away.

Who Invented Soap?

The Babylonians were the one who invented soap at 2800 B.C. They discovered that combining fats, namely animal fats, with wood ash produced a substance capable of easier cleaning. The first soap was used to wash wool used in textile industry.

Skin Anatomy

The skin is the body's largest organ. It covers the entire body. It serves as a protective shield against heat, light, injury, and infection. The skin also

- Regulates body temperature
- Stores water and fat
- Is a sensory organ
- Prevents water loss
- Prevents entry of bacteria
- Acts as a barrier between the organism and its environment. [7]

Skin takes on different thickness, colour, and texture all over your body. For example, your head contains more hair follicles than anywhere else. But the soles of your feet have none. In addition, the soles of your feet and the palms of your hands are much thicker than skin on others areas of body.

FUNCTIONS OF SKIN

Skin performs the following functions:

Protection: An anatomical barrier from pathogens and damage between the internal and external

environment in bodily defense, Langerhans cells in the skin are part of the adaptive immune system.

Sensation: Contains a variety of nerve endings that react to heat and cold, touch, pressure, vibration, and tissue injury, see soma to sensory system and haptics.

Heat regulation: The skin contains a blood supply far greater than its requirements which allows precise control of energy loss by radiation, convection and conduction. Dilated blood vessels increase perfusion and heat loss, while constricted vessels greatly reduce cutaneous blood flow and conserve heat.

Control of evaporation: The skin provides a relatively dry and semi- impermeable barrier to fluid loss. Loss of this function contributes to the massive fluid loss in burns.

Aesthetics and communication: Others see our skin and can assess our mood, physical state and attractiveness.

Storage and synthesis: Acts as a storage center for lipids and water, as well as a means of synthesis of vitamin D by action of UV on certain parts of the skin.

Water resistance: The skin acts as a water-resistant barrier so essential nutrients aren't washed out of the body.

PHARMACOGENETIC CHARACTERS

BITTER ORANGE PEEL

Fig no.1: Orange Peel

Family :- Rosaceae

Scientific name :- citrus sinensis

Kingdom :- plantae

Common name :- Bitter orange Peel

Biological source:-

The orange peel is the fresh or dried outer part of the pericarp of Citrus aurantium Linn, belonging to family Rosaceae.

Geographical Source:-

It is mainly cultivated in India, China, Spain, Madeira, Sicily, Milla, and Morocco

Morphological characteristic

It has an aromatic odor, bitter and aromatic taste. The oil of Bitter Orange Peel is pale yellow liquid; it is soluble in four volumes of alcohol. Neutral to litmus paper and specific gravity at 25°C is 0.842 to 0.848. Bitter orange peel contains of 1 to 2.5% volatile oil.

Cultivation and collection

1. Source: Orange peels can be collected from:
 - Fresh orange juice production facilities
 - Food processing industries
 - Local markets or households.
2. Peel collection methods: Peels can be collected manually or mechanically.
3. Drying: Peels are dried to remove excess moisture, either through:
 - Sun drying
 - Machine drying
 - Freeze-drying

Uses

It is used as aromatic, stomachic, carminative, and flavoring agent, it is used particularly in fish liver oil preparations and liver extract. The oil is used chiefly as a flavoring agent, used in the oil of

turpentine in chronic bronchitis. It is nonirritant to the kidneys and pleasant to take.

Side Effects

Topical use of orange peel in individuals with a sensitive skin type can lead to irritation of the skin. With the use of essential oil, side effects include redness and inflammation of the skin, which would resolve after some time.

Chemical constituents

Bitter orange peel contains of 1 to 2.5% volatile oil. The principle component of volatile oil is 90% limonene and small quantities of aldehydes central, citronellal, bitter amorphous glycoside like aurantia Marin and it's acid; hesperidin, is hesperidin, vitamin C, and Pectin.

Fig no.1.1: Hesperidin

Fig no.1.2: Isohesperidin

Fig no.1.3: Vitamin C

HONEY

Fig no.2: Honey

Family:- Apidae

Scientific name:- Apis mellifera

Kingdom:- Animalia

Common name:- Honey

Biological source:-

Honey is a viscid and sweet secretion stored in the honey comb by various species of bees, such as Apis mellifera, Apis dorsata, Apis florea, Apis indica and other species of Apis, belonging to family Apidae (Order: Hymenoptera).

Geographical Source:-

Honey is available in abundance in Africa, India, Jamaica, Australia, California, Chili, Great Britain and New Zealand.

Morphological characteristic.

Generally, Apis mellifera are red/brown with black bands and orange yellow rings on abdomen. They have hair on thorax and less hair on abdomen. They also have a pollen basket on their hind legs. Honeybee legs are mostly dark brown/black.

Cultivation and collection

Honey consumption has high nutritional and therapeutic values. The phytochemical compounds

in honey depends mainly on various factors, floral source, honey type, concentration, and bee type. These factors affect the biological activities of each type of honey.

Uses

Honey shows mild laxative, bactericidal, sedative, antiseptic and alkaline characters. It prevents infection and promotes healing. Honey works quicker than many antibiotics because it is easily absorbed into the blood stream. It is also useful in healing of carbuncles, chaps, scalds, whitlows and skin inflammation; as vermicide; locally as an excipient, in the treatment of aphthae and other infection of the oral mucous membrane.

Side Effects

- Wheezing and other asthmatic symptoms
- Dizziness
- Nausea
- Vomiting
- Weakness
- Excessive perspiration
- Fainting
- Irregular heart rhythms (arrhythmias)
- Stinging after topical application
- Honey might affect blood sugar levels

Chemical constituents

The average composition of honey is as follows: Moisture 14–24%, Dextrose 23– 36%, Levulose (Fructose) 30–47%, Sucrose 0.4–6%, Dextrin and Gums 0–7% and Ash 0.1–0.8%. Besides, it is found to contain small amounts of essential oil, beeswax, pollen grains, formic acid, acetic acid, succinic acid, maltose, dextrin, coloring pigments, vitamins and an admixture of enzymes, for example, diastase, invertase and enolase. Interestingly, the sugar contents in honey varies widely from one country to another as it is exclusively governed by the source of the nectar

(availability of frag-mint flowers in the region) and also the enzymatic activity solely controlling the conversion into honey.

Fig no.2.1: acetic acid

Fig no.2.2. formic acid

Fig no.2.3: succinic acid

ALOE

Fig no.3.1: Aloe vera

Family :- Asphodelaceae

Scientific name :- Aloe vera

Kingdom :- plantae

Common name :- Aloe vera

Biological source:-

Aloe is the dried juice collected by incision, from the bases of the leaves of various species of Aloe. Aloe perryi Baker, Aloe vera Linn or Aloe barbadense Mill and Aloe ferox Miller., belonging to family Liliaceae. Aloe perryi Baker is found in Socotra and Zanzibar islands and in their neighboring areas and so the aloes obtained from this species is known as Doctrine or Zanzibar aloe.

Geographical Source:-

Aloes are indigenous to East and South Africa, but have been introduced into the West Indies and into tropical countries, and will even flourish in the countries bordering on the Mediterranean .[8]

Morphological characteristic:-

Aloe vera is a stemless or very short-stemmed plant growing to 60–100 centimeters (24–39 inches) tall, spreading by offsets. The leaves are thick and fleshy, green to grey-green, with some varieties showing white flecks on their upper and lower stem surfaces

Cultivation and collection:-

It is an evergreen perennial growing to 0.8 m by 1 m at a slow rate. The plant prefers light (sandy) and medium (loamy) soils, requires well-drained soil and can grow in nutritionally poor soil. The plant prefers acid, neutral and basic (alkaline) soils. It cannot grow in the shade. It requires dry or moist soil and can tolerate drought. They are xerophytic plant. It can be propagated by seeds. Seeds are sown in the spring in a warm green house. The seed usually germinates in 1–6 months at 16°C. The seedlings are transferred to the pots containing well-drained soil. They are allowed to grow in sunny part for at least their first two winters. The offsets will be available, usually in spring. The plants produce offsets quite freely and they can be divided at any time of the year as long

as it is warm enough to encourage fresh root growth to allow reestablishment of the plants. Young offsets are planted in the soil after the rainy season in rows situated at a distance of 60 cm.

Uses:-

The drug Aloes is one of the safest and stimulating purga-tives, in higher doses may act as abortifacient. Its action is exerted mainly on the large intestine; also it is useful as a vermifuge. The plant is emmenagogue, emollient, stimulant, stomachic, tonic and vulnerary. Extracts of the plant have antibacterial activity. The clear gel of the leaf makes an excellent treatment for wounds, burns and other skin disorders, placing a protective coat over the affected area, speeding up the

Side Effects:-

Aloe latex or whole-leaf extract taken orally might be unsafe and is likely unsafe in high doses. Taking 1 gram, a day of aloe latex for several days can cause acute kidney failure and can be fatal. Aloe latex might also have the potential to cause cancer. Other side effects include abdominal cramps and diarrhea.

Chemical constituents:-

The most important constituents of Aloes are the three isomers of Aloins, Barbaloin, β -barbaloin and is barbaloin, which constitute the so-called 'crystalline' Aloin, present in the drug at from 10 to 30%. Other constituents are amorphous Aloin, resin, emodin and Aloe-emodin. Barbaloin is present in all the varieties; it is slightly yellow colored, bitter, water soluble, crystalline glycoside. Is barbaloin is a crystalline substance, present in Curacao aloe and in trace amount in Cape aloe and absent in Doctrine and Zanzibar aloe. The chief constituents of Doctrine and Zanzibar aloe are Barbaloin and β -Bar

Fig no.3.1: β -Barbaloin

Fig no.3.2. Barbaloin

Fig no.3.3 Isobarbaloin

SANDALLWOOD

Fig no.4.1 Sandalwood

Family :- Santalaceae

Scientific name :- Santalum

Kingdom :- plantae

Common name :- Sandalwood

Biological source:-

Sandalwood oil is obtained by distillation of sandalwood, *Santalum album* Linn., belonging to family Santalaceae

Geographical Source:-

Sandal is a small to medium-sized, evergreen semiparasitic tree found in the dry regions of peninsular India from Vindhya Mountains southwards, especially in Mysore and Tamil Nadu. It has also been introduced in Rajasthan, parts of U.P., M.P., and Orissa

Morphological characteristic:-

Leaves thin, usually opposite, ovate or ovate elliptical, 3-8 x 3-5 cm, glabrous and shining green above, glaucous and slightly paler beneath; tip rounded or pointed; stalk grooved, 5-15 cm long; venation noticeably reticulate.

Cultivation and collection:-

Sandalwood Tree Seeds. Planting and Spacing in Sandalwood Cultivation:- Usually seeds collected from plants age of 15 to 20 years in August to March is best for its growth and yield. These collected plants should be dried up and well-treated before sowing on nursery beds.

Uses:-

In traditional medicine, sandalwood oil has been used as an antiseptic and astringent, and for the treatment of headache, stomachache, and urinary and genital disorders. In India, the essential oil, emulsion, or paste of sandalwood is used in the treatment of inflammatory and eruptive skin diseases

Side Effects:-

White sandalwood can also cause itching, nausea, and stomach upset. When applied to the skin: There isn't enough reliable information to know if white sandalwood is safe in amounts greater than those contained in cosmetics. Contact with white sandalwood can cause allergic skin reactions in some people.

Chemical constituents:-

The main odorous and medicinal constituent of Sandal-wood is sotalol. This primary sesquiterpene alcohol forms more than 90% of the oil and is present as a mixture of two isomers, α -sotalol and β -sotalol, the former predominating. The other constituents reported are hydrocarbons santene, nor-santene, α -, and β - santolinas

Fig no.4.1 α -, and β - santalenes

Fig no.4.2 hydrocarbons santene

5. MULTANI MITTI

Fig no. 5.1 Multani Mitti

Common name : Multani Mitti .

Scientific name : Fullers Earth .

Geographical Source : primarily originates from the Multan region (now in Pakistan) and the Barmer district of Rajasthan, India.

Appearance: Multani Mitti typically presents as a light beige or off-white powder with a fine texture. It can also have a slightly yellowish hue.

Texture: When dry, it should feel fine and smooth, not gritty.

Odour: It is generally odorless.

Application: Multani Mitti can be used in various ways, such as mixed with water or rose water to create a paste.

Multani Mitti (Calcium bentonite) Multani mitti helps skin by different ways like diminishing pore sizes, removing blackheads and whiteheads fading freckles, soothing sunburns, cleansing skin, improving blood circulation, complexion, reducing acne and blemishes and gives a glowing effect to a skin as they contain healthy nutrients. Multani mitti is rich magnesium chloride.

Skin Uses:

Oil Absorption:

Multani mitti is particularly effective for oily and acne-prone skin due to its ability to absorb excess sebum and oil, helping to unclog pores and reduce breakouts.

Deep Cleansing:

It effectively removes dirt, impurities, and dead skin cells, leaving skin feeling refreshed and radiant.

Exfoliation:

Multani mitti acts as a gentle exfoliator, helping to remove dead skin cells and promote a smoother complexion.

Soothing and Cooling:

It has a natural cooling effect, making it beneficial for soothing sunburns, reducing inflammation, and calming irritated skin.

Skin Tightening and Anti-Aging:

Multani mitti can help tighten skin pores, reduce the appearance of fine lines and wrinkles, and promote a more youthful complexion Treatment of Acne, Blemishes.

Possible Side Effects

1. Dryness: Multani Mitti can be drying to the skin, especially if used excessively or on sensitive skin.
2. Irritation: Some individuals may experience skin irritation, redness, or itching due to the clay's abrasive nature or allergic reactions.
3. Allergic reactions: Rarely, people may be allergic to Multani Mitti, which can cause more severe reactions like hives, swelling, or difficulty breathing.

4. Clogged pores: If not properly rinsed, Multani Mitti can clog pores, especially in acne-prone skin.

Chemical constituents :

Multani mitti is clay made up of primarily Aluminium Silicate with trace amounts of other impurities. The composition varies according to the region from where it is mined. This clay consisting of SiO₂- 47%, Al₂O₃, 23.3%, Fe₂O₃6.95%, CaO 2.9%.

AIM & OBJECTIVE:

AIM:

This review focuses on plants currently used and those with a high potency for the future development of anti-acne products.

1. Assess patient compliance in acne vulgaris.
2. To purifies and refreshes your skin
3. By regular use helps prevents from acne, blackheads and pigmentations.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Chemicals, plants and their extracts:

Table No:1

SR.NO	CHEMICALS	QUANTITY
1	Orange peel powder	2gm
2	Sandalwood powder	1gm
3	honey	1.5ml
4	Alovera gel	1gm
5	Soap base	50gm
6	Rose water	3ml
7	Multani mitti	4gm

METHODOLOGY:

Formulation of oil removing Herbal soap Soap

1. Weigh all the ingredients which is solid
2. Take glycerine soap base in container and melt it using double water bath.

3. After melting the soap base add powder of solution in soap base.
4. Then add berberis oil in the melted soap base and stir it well.
5. After this add all excipients and mix it properly.
6. Then finally stop the heating and add essential oil for the fragrance.
7. This prepared solution is then poured in the soap mould for the shape of the soap.
8. Finally, the soap is ready.

Evaluation of Soap:

The following are the Evaluation parameters for medicinal soap:

1. Physical Appearance
2. Thermal Stability
3. Determination of pH
4. Foaming Stability
5. Consistency
6. Foam retention
7. Hardness test

Physical appearance:

The prepared formulation of soap were evaluated in terms of clarity. The prepared soap shows brown colour. Determination of Clarity, Colour and Odours Clarity and colour was checked by naked eyes against white background, the odour was smelled. [9]

Thermal stability:

Thermal stability of the formulation was determined by the humidity chamber controlled at 60-70/ RH at room temperature. This soap is mainly stable at room temperature, increases it mainly unstable.

Determination of pH:

5 to 6 g of the soap was weighted accurately in a 100ml beaker 40ml water was added and dispersed the soap in it .the pH of solution is determined by PH meter; the pH of soap is 8.7.

Microbial growth:

Using agar plates the plates were placed in to the incubator and are incubator at 37c for 24hours compared with standard.

Foaming ability and foam stability:

Foaming ability was determined by using cylinder shake method brietal 40ml of the formulation soap solution was placed graduate cylinder. It was covered with and hand and shaken 10 times the total volume of the foam content after 1 min of shaking recovered foam stability was evaluated by recording the foam volume after 1min and 4 minis 80to 93/ foam formed.

Consistency:

The consistency of formulated soap was determined by hand. Take pinch of soap and rubbed it with finger.

Foam retention :

About 1% soap solution was prepared and from this, 25ml was taken in a 100ml measuring cylinder. The cylinder was covered with hand and shaken for 10 min. The volume of foam at 1 min intervals for 4 min was recorded.

Hardness test :

The hardness test is done with the instrument Pfister type instrument. The hardness of soap is 6.5.

Use of soap

- Treat acne antibacterial properties of neem fight acne causing bacteria which help in the treatment and prevention of acne.
- Tackles blackheads and whiteheads.
- Aloe Vera shows moisturizer it is moisture the skin without giving it a greasy feel. So, it is perfect for anyone with an oily skin.
- It also fights sunburn or acne. This soap is mainly used all skin problem. [9]

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

The oil removing Herbal soap was formulated by using the abovementioned chemicals. And also, all evaluation test which are essential for testing also evaluated. The oil removing Herbal soap was formulated which was chemical property was successfully evaluated using different evaluation parameter as mention above. The formulated soap applies to the face of patient and give the smoothing softening effect to the skin.

Observation Table :

Evaluation parameters	Observation
Physical appearance	Colour: brown
Thermal Stability	Stable at room temperature , melt at 60 degree celcius
Determination of PH	8.5
Stability studies	No colour change.
Microbial growth	No microbial growth
Foaming ability	Stable soap
Foam retention	1.6cm

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

The oil removing Herbal soap was formulated by using the abovementioned chemicals. And also, all evaluation test which are essential for testing also evaluated. The oil removing Herbal soap was formulated which was chemical property was successfully evaluated using different evaluation parameter as mention above. The formulated soap applies to the face of patient and give the smoothing softening effect to the skin.

Conclusion and Summary

The purpose of the present investigation was to formulated and evaluated the anti-acne so a topical delivery system for the treatment of *Acne vulgaris*. The stability test showed that the formulations were stable at room temperature for two year and at 45°C for 3 months. Hence it can concluded that the anti-acne soap was prepared by using flax seed, Aloe vera, Turmeric, Honey, Orang Oil, Neem Oil, Sodium Lauryl Sulphate, Sodium Hydroxide, Benzoyl Peroxide which having smoothening, softening, Cleaning property during formulation we have take care about all the errors and formulated soap successfully with all the anti-bacterial activity and reduce the scaly red skin (seborrhoea), pinheads (papules), blackheads and whiteheads (comedowns), large papules (nodules), and sometimes scarring (pimples) by using different chemical like Benzoyl Peroxide and Neem Oil. For emulated soap was evaluated using different evaluation parameters.

Future Prospective:

Through in this study is has been proved that anti-arcane soap can act as a useful tool for topical in delivery system in the treatment of the scaly red skin (seborrhoea), pinheads (papules), blackheads and whiteheads (comedowns), large papules (nodules), and sometimes scarring (pimples). Further clinical and pharmacokinetic studies are

required to export the potential of this system for used in humans

CONCLUSION

Oily skin is a common chief complaint of dermatologic patients. While sebaceous glands play an integral role in cutaneous function, they are troublesome for some patients when sebum is excessively produced. Numerous treatment options exist to help tame sebum excretion rates, but a clear consensus on the preferred treatment regimen is yet to be described. Each treatment option comes with its own inherent advantages and disadvantages that should be discussed with patients at length, and treatment can then be personalized to each patient's needs. As more knowledge is gained about the complex pathogenesis behind oily skin, more novel and targeted therapies will hopefully be developed to more satisfactorily treat oily skin. The knowledge of various medicinal plants used by the people of seems to be well known to its culture and tradition.³ There is a great demand for the herbal face cosmetics. In general, botanicals provide different vitamins, antioxidants, various oils, essential oils, proteins, hydrocolloids, terpenoids and other bioactive molecules are used in herbal face care preparations. In the present scenario many people need cure and care for various skin problems without side effects. Herbal ingredients opened the way to formulate cosmetic products without any harmful effect. Herbal face wash and herbal face creams are considered as sustaining and productive way to advance the appearance of face skin.

RESULTS

All the three formulations F1H, F2H, F3H showed good appearance, PH, adequate viscosity and no phase separation was observed. Also, the formulations F1H, F2H, F3H showed no redness,

erythema and irritation during irritancy study and they were easily washable. All the three formulations F1H, F2H, F3H were stable at room temperature.

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